

Community-Grounded Authenticity at Bamiyan: Afghan Perspectives on AI-Mediated Heritage Reconstruction

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Abstract

Digital and AI-mediated reconstructions of destroyed heritage monuments have advanced in archaeological modelling, prompt engineering and expert-guided evaluation, yet the Bamiyan literature paid limited empirical attention on how Afghan respondents themselves define authenticity, acceptable reconstruction, and the representation of absence. This article addresses that gap through a questionnaire study of sixty-two Afghan respondents and situates the findings within the authors' earlier reconstruction workflow. Support for reconstruction was high, but respondents did not equate acceptable reconstruction with visual replacement alone: alongside material fidelity, they prioritised historical context, cultural meaning, associated skills and knowledge, and selected sensory elements. Concerns about AI centred on the oversimplification of cultural meaning, while views on the inclusion of Hazara voices indicated continuing uncertainty about reconstruction governance. No meaningful differences emerged across the demographic sub-groups tested. The article argues that technically plausible and expert-validated reconstruction remains incomplete unless community-grounded authenticity is made visible in the reconstruction process. It accordingly proposes that reconstruction outputs published from AI-mediated workflows should record provenance, rupture, and governance visibility as minimum publication conditions.

Keywords: Bamiyan Buddhas; community-grounded authenticity; digital heritage; generative AI reconstruction; Nara Document; participatory heritage

1. Introduction

The Taliban's destruction of the Buddhas of Bamiyan in March 2001 removed two monumental rock-cut sculptures from the cultural landscape of central Afghanistan and transformed the site into a continuing problem of heritage reconstruction, representation, and loss. The act was widely treated as a turning point in debates on cultural-heritage protection in conflict (Flood, 2002; Lostal & Vasconcelos Vilaça, 2015). Since then, Bamiyan has been the subject of photogrammetric documentation, long-term conservation and virtual-reality planning, remote-sensing assessment of the wider archaeological landscape, and, more recently, generative-AI reconstruction workflows (Arzomand & Kalganova, 2026; Grün et al., 2004; Hammer et al., 2018; Nagaoka, 2020; Remondino, 2011; Toubekis et al., 2017). Critical heritage scholarship has accompanied this technical record with parallel concern for memory, erasure, and representational authority at the site (Connerton, 2008; Flood, 2002; Lostal & Vasconcelos Vilaça, 2015; Macdonald, 2008; Risam, 2018; Stobiecka, 2020). What remains comparatively thin is primary empirical evidence on how Afghan respondents themselves understand authenticity, loss, and acceptable reconstruction at Bamiyan.

This article addresses that empirical gap. Where Afghan perspectives appear in the existing literature, they are more often mediated through secondary scholarship or institutional documents than examined through primary data collected from Afghan respondents themselves (Dupree, 2002; Monsutti, 2005). That asymmetry matters because the authors' earlier reconstruction work has already identified the under-representation of Afghan and Buddhist-practitioner perspectives as a limitation. The present study extends that research programme by adding the community layer that the earlier studies identified as missing. Earlier work in this research programme established AI-assisted reconstruction methodology and formalised it through the Heritage-Aligned Reconstruction Framework (HARF), with a subsequent paired computational–expert evaluation showing that similarity-based metrics and specialist judgement can diverge on stylistic and iconographic grounds (Arzomand et al., 2024, 2026; Arzomand & Kalganova, 2026). Computational plausibility does not on its own resolve questions of historical adequacy, particularly where stylistic judgement and community-grounded perspectives remain underrepresented. The present study responds to that limitation directly.

This study advances a focused argument. A reconstruction workflow may be evidentially disciplined and expert-validated, yet remain incomplete if the terms of authenticity, absence, and legitimacy are never examined from the perspective of those most closely connected to the site. Drawing on questionnaire responses from sixty-two Afghan respondents, the article shows that support for reconstruction does not equate to support for seamless visual replacement alone. Respondents attached importance not only to material fidelity, but also to historical context, cultural meaning, associated skills and knowledge, selected sensory dimensions, and the visibility of rupture. On that basis, the article proposes a community-grounded extension to AI-mediated reconstruction at Bamiyan centred on provenance, rupture, and governance. Three questions structure the analysis: how Afghan respondents conceptualise authenticity, loss, and acceptable reconstruction at Bamiyan; whether views on reconstruction, sensory inclusion, and governance vary across the demographic sub-groups within the sample; and how these findings should inform an AI-mediated reconstruction workflow previously assessed through computational and expert evaluation.

2. Bamiyan in the Literature: Post-2001 Documentation and the Question of Authenticity

The Bamiyan case is well documented technically, but less well examined through primary respondent evidence. The Buddhas were monumental rock-cut sculptures dating to the sixth and seventh centuries, set within a wider Buddhist monastic complex along the Silk Road and surrounded by hundreds of decorated meditation cave structures and mural remains (Grün et al., 2004; Klimburg-Salter, 1989; Petzet, 2009). The valley's contemporary population is predominantly Hazara, a Shia Muslim ethnic group concentrated in the central highlands of Afghanistan, including Bamiyan, Daikundi, Ghazni, and Samangan (Monsutti, 2005). Hazara communities have lived in the valley for centuries, cultivated the land around the cliffs, and continued to act as residents and custodians of the wider site through successive political regimes, while also maintaining their own reinterpretation of the statues' identity. Indeed, in Hazara oral traditions, the statues in Bamiyan are not understood

solely as Buddhas but are woven into local legends and associated with heroic figures known as Salsal and Shamama, tied to the region’s cultural landscape (Singh, 2022). Hazara have also been subject to repeated persecution, including during the 1990s Taliban advance on the central highlands and again after 2021. Acknowledging the Hazara presence in the context of Bamiyan reconstruction is therefore not identity-labelling but a substantive point about custodianship and about which community bears the local consequences of reconstruction decisions taken elsewhere.

Post-2001 responses to the site have been technically diverse and institutionally distributed. Photogrammetric reconstruction of the Great Buddha was carried out by Grün and colleagues at ETH Zurich on the basis of pre-destruction imagery, establishing the principal dimensional record on which subsequent work has drawn (Grün et al., 2004). Long-term conservation and virtual-reality planning have been led by Toubekis, Jansen and the RWTH Aachen team in cooperation with ICOMOS Germany, supporting evaluation of physical-restoration options for the niches and surrounding fabric (Petzet, 2009; Toubekis et al., 2017). Remote-sensing assessment of the wider Bamiyan cultural landscape has been undertaken by Hammer and collaborators, extending the documentary record beyond the niches themselves (Hammer et al., 2018). Earlier Japanese cultural missions in the 1970s produced measured drawings and architectural surveys that remain the most precise records of niche geometry. These institutional efforts converge on documentation and physical-restoration planning rather than on community consultation. The 2017 UNESCO symposium, whose proceedings were edited by Nagaoka (2020), presents positions ranging from anastylosis and partial reconstruction to non-reconstruction, alongside debates about what authenticity means when the original fabric is almost entirely lost (Holtorf, 2020; Jokilehto, 2020; Rössler, 2020). The consensus that emerges is methodologically instructive and substantively limited: it confirms that authenticity at Bamiyan cannot be reduced to material fidelity alone, but it is authored almost entirely by international experts and institutions rather than by Afghan respondents. Table 1 summarises these post-2001 efforts and locates the contribution of the present article in relation to them.

Table 1. Post-2001 reconstruction approaches to the Bamiyan Buddhas, the institutional teams involved, and what each approach addresses and does not address.

Approach	Centre / lead team	Date	Output Type	Addresses	Doesn't Address
Photogrammetric reconstruction	ETH Zurich (Grün et al.)	2004	Dimensional model of Great Buddha	Geometry, proportion, scale	Community meaning; absence; sensory layer
Long-term conservation and VR planning	RWTH Aachen / ICOMOS Germany (Petzet, Toubekis, Jansen)	2009–2017	VR environment; restoration scenarios	Physical-restoration evaluation; niche fabric	Community consultation; oral testimony
Remote-sensing landscape assessment	Hammer et al.	2018	Damage and landscape mapping	Wider archaeological landscape	Site-specific representational ethics

Approach	Centre / lead team	Date	Output Type	Addresses	Doesn't Address
UNESCO symposium synthesis	UNESCO / Nagaoka (Ed.)	2020	Edited volume, multi-author	Authenticity debates, restoration options	Primary Afghan respondent data
Generative AI reconstruction (HARF)	Authors	2024–2026	AI-generated imagery, expert-validated	Visual hypothesis generation, evidentiary discipline	Community-epistemic layer (this article)

The second body of literature concerns authenticity in heritage studies. The Venice Charter (ICOMOS, 1964) defines restoration as preserving and revealing aesthetic and historic value while distinguishing original material from reconstructive intervention. The Nara Document on Authenticity (ICOMOS, 1994) widens authenticity beyond material fabric to include form and design, use and function, traditions and techniques, location and setting, and spirit and feeling, while rejecting any single universal standard across cultures. The London Charter (Denard, 2009) and the Seville Principles (López-Menchero Bendicho & Grande, 2011) translate these obligations into computer-based heritage visualisation by requiring evidentiary grounding, paradata, and explicit marking of inference and uncertainty. Across the heritage-studies literature that runs alongside these standards, authenticity is increasingly treated not as a property inhering in an object, but as a relation between people, objects, and places that must be negotiated rather than simply inspected (Harrison, 2012; Jones, 2010; Kirshenblatt-gimblett, 2004; Silberman, 2012; Smith, 2006). This echoes M. Forte’s elaboration of Gibson’s concept of affordances, according to which cultural heritage environments afford multiple possibilities for social perception, interaction, and cultural interpretation (Forte, 2024).

Recent scholarship has distinguished several senses of authenticity that operate at this site, including historical, material, experiential, community, and procedural-transparent authenticity (Jones, 2010; Silberman, 2012). This article adopts the relational sense established in the Nara Document and developed by Jones (2010) and uses the term community-grounded authenticity as shorthand for authenticity constituted through the relations that descendant and custodial communities maintain with a heritage site, and that therefore cannot be adjudicated without their participation (ICOMOS, 1994; Jones, 2010) Using this as the master term keeps the analysis on a single relational concept rather than across the neighbouring concepts of legitimacy, epistemic authority, and representational accountability, which are treated here as components of community-grounded authenticity rather than as rival organising terms.

The empirical gap is narrow but important. No published study of the Bamiyan case treats Afghan respondents themselves as the epistemic source on what authenticity requires for this site. Within the authors’ own research programme, the same pattern has held until now: HARF was validated through a thirty-three-expert international panel, and the paired evaluation through five Bamiyan specialists (Arzomand et al., 2026; Arzomand & Kalganova, 2026), neither of which substitutes for community testimony. The present article begins to supply that community layer and, in doing so, extends the existing technical workflow in a direction its own limitations have already identified as necessary.

3. Methods

This study is based on an online questionnaire titled *Memory, Absence, and Digital Reconstruction of Lost Cultural Heritage in the Bamiyan Valley*, approved by the Brunel University of London Research Ethics Committee under reference 50187-LR-Jan/2025-53624-2. The participant information sheet stated the study's purpose, expected completion time, the voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw up to the point of submission, data-handling procedures, and the researcher's contact details. Consent was indicated by continuing past the consent page. Participation was voluntary, informed, and pseudonymous, and no direct identifying information was collected; the questionnaire recorded demographic categories and a timestamp rather than names or contact details. Responses were stored in the university's secure repository under UK GDPR. No identifiable quotations are used in this article. The full ethics statement, consent procedure, anonymisation measures, and quotation policy are provided in Section S1 of the Methodology Supplement.

The instrument comprised forty-six items organised in six thematic blocks: demographic context; connection and memory; interpretations of destruction; reconstruction preferences and ethical considerations; intangible and sensory dimensions; and open reflections. Items combined single-select, multi-select, and short open-ended formats. The instrument was refined through three pilot rounds ($n = 5$, $n = 4$, $n = 3$; where n denotes the number of respondents in each pilot round) with Afghan pilot respondents drawn from diaspora academic networks. Pilot feedback was used to refine wording and remove double-barrelled items. The questionnaire was provided in English, with a Dari/Farsi and Pashto translation available on request, and quoted open-ended responses were either submitted in English or translated by the first author with back-translation checks conducted on a subset. The full instrument is reproduced in Section S2 of the Methodology Supplement.

Recruitment used purposive and snowball sampling through Afghan diaspora community organisations, academic networks in the UK, Europe, and North America, and local contacts inside Afghanistan. The resulting sample ($N = 62$, where N denotes the total number of respondents) is a convenience sample of Afghan respondents reachable through those channels, not a probability sample of the Afghan population. A goodness-of-fit comparison of the named-ethnicity portion of the sample against widely cited estimates of Afghanistan's ethnic composition returned $\chi^2(2) = 10.49$, $p = .005$, with Hazara respondents over-represented relative to the wider population. This is consistent with the study's substantive focus on the Bamiyan Valley, but it confirms that the sample should not be treated as nationally representative; the analysis therefore reports within-sample patterns and does not generalise to Afghan respondents more broadly. Full demographic breakdown, current-location detail, and sample-composition analysis are provided in Section S3 and Tables S1–S5, while the population-comparison exercise is reported in Section S7 and Table S17 of the Methodology Supplement.

Closed items are reported as counts and proportions with Wilson 95% confidence intervals. Multi-select items report selection counts that exceed N by design and are interpreted as overlapping endorsements rather than mutually exclusive categories. Broad subgroup contrasts on core reconstruction and governance items are reported with chi-square or Fisher tests and bias-corrected

Cramér’s V, but the sample size and thinness of several demographic cells do not support regression modelling or fine-grained three-way contrasts. Open-ended responses were analysed thematically (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Coding proceeded in two passes: an initial inductive pass to generate candidate themes, followed by a second pass that cross-referenced those themes against the closed-item findings. Coding detail, including the blinded subset check, is provided in Section S9 of the Methodology Supplement. Quotations are presented only in anonymised form and are not accompanied by combined ethnicity-by-gender-by-country identifiers, because cell sizes at those intersections are too small to permit such attribution without re-identification risk. Full descriptive tables, subgroup contrasts, the Hazara sub-sample breakdown, thematic coding detail, and reproducibility materials are provided in Sections S4-S6, and S8-S10 of the Methodology Supplement, including Tables S6–S19 where relevant.

4. Results

Table 2 reports the headline closed-item findings. Support for reconstruction was high, although respondents did not equate acceptable reconstruction with visual replacement. Material fidelity, cultural connection, physical reconstruction, sensory inclusion, hybrid past-present representation of absence, and concern about AI-mediated oversimplification of cultural meaning were all selected by majorities or near-majorities. Counts are out of $N = 62$ unless otherwise stated; multi-select totals exceed N by design, and full descriptive tables are reproduced in Section S4-S5 and Tables S6–S15 of the Methodology Supplement.

Table 2. Headline proportions with Wilson 95% confidence intervals ($N = 62$).

Item	n	Proportion	95% CI
Support reconstruction (Yes)	51	82.3%	71.0–89.8%
Material fidelity prioritised (multi-select)	52	83.9%	72.8–91.0%
Cultural connection selected (multi-select)	48	77.4%	65.6–86.0%
Physical reconstruction preferred (multi-select)	49	79.0%	67.4–87.3%
Sensory elements should be included (Yes)	38	61.3%	48.8–72.4%
Hybrid past-present representation of absence	37	59.7%	47.3–71.0%
AI concern: oversimplification of cultural meaning	36	58.1%	45.7–69.5%
Hazara voices perceived as included	19	30.6%	20.6–43.0%
Hazara voices: don't know	31	50.0%	37.9–62.1%

Ethnic self-identification comprised Pashtun (26, 41.9%), Hazara (13, 21.0%), Tajik (12, 19.4%), Arab (2), and Sadaat (1); six respondents indicated that ethnicity did not matter to them, and two responses were missing. The age distribution was 21–35 (35), 36–50 (18), over 50 (8), and under 20 (1); gender, where reported, was male (43) and female (18), with one unspecified response. Twenty-five respondents resided in Afghanistan and thirty-six across the diaspora, with country of residence not

reported by one respondent. Pre-destruction familiarity with the statues was almost universal, with 59 of 62 respondents reporting prior knowledge of the site.

Multiple, overlapping modes of connection were reported (Figure 1). Cultural connection through stories, ancestry, and traditions was the dominant mode (48, 77.4%; 95% CI 65.6–86.0%), followed by emotional connection (24, 38.7%), personal connection through family history or visits (18, 29.0%), political connection (15, 24.2%), and spiritual connection (10, 16.1%). Three respondents reported no strong connection to the site. Intergenerational transmission was substantial: 33 of 62 respondents (53.2%) stated that their family or community had shared stories about the statues, and 24 reported continuing to remember those stories in detail. Pre-destruction familiarity was acquired predominantly through schooling, family narrative, and media exposure, and several open-ended responses referred to the statues by their local names *Salsal* and *Shahmama*, indicating that intergenerational naming practice survives even among respondents who learned of the site only after its destruction. The statues are accordingly framed within the sample as inheritances of cultural and civilisational identity, with devotional registers occupying a clear minority position.

Figure 1. Modes through which respondents reported a connection to the Bamiyan Buddhas (multi-select; N = 62). Respondents could select more than one mode, so totals exceed N by design. Counts and percentages are shown alongside each bar.

Open-ended responses interpreted the 2001 destruction as politically motivated. The act was repeatedly characterised as a message directed at the international community, as targeted violence against the Hazara population, and as the imposition of an exclusionary ideology. A minority of responses described the religious justification advanced at the time as a misinterpretation of Islamic scholarly tradition. The present article does not adjudicate that theological dispute and confines its claim to the empirical observation that respondents did not treat the religious framing as settled. The interpretive pattern is consistent with academic accounts of the destruction as political signalling, in which the 2001 act is read against the longer history of contested heritage and political erasure (Flood, 2002; Lostal & Vasconcelos Vilaça, 2015).

Support for reconstruction was 51 of 62 respondents (82.3%; 95% CI 71.0–89.8%), with 6 uncertain (9.7%) and 5 opposed (8.1%) (Figure 2A). The substantive finding lies in the operational meaning that respondents attached to "reconstruction", which extended well beyond visual completeness (Figure 2B). Multi-select responses on what should be reconstructed prioritised material fidelity to the original (52, 83.9%); selection of non-material aspects was substantial, comprising the skills and knowledge associated with the statues' creation (24, 38.7%), the destruction and its historical context (21, 33.9%), and the meaning and symbolism of the statues (20, 32.3%); four respondents indicated that nothing should be reconstructed. Modal preference was physical reconstruction (49, 79.0%), followed by digital imagery (19, 30.6%), VR/AR (18, 29.0%), and holograms (14, 22.6%); 11 respondents recorded no preference. The sample therefore treats physical reconstruction as the primary modality and digital reconstruction as complementary. Governance preferences were distributed across multiple actors: UNESCO-style organisations (39, 62.9%), Afghan archaeologists and cultural historians (37, 59.7%), heritage scholars (26, 41.9%), the Afghan government (25, 40.3%), the local Hazara community (18, 29.0%), all parties equally (16, 25.8%), and Buddhist monks (13, 21.0%). Guiding principles were headed by historical accuracy (52, 83.9%) and economic considerations including tourism (40, 64.5%); cultural resistance or protest (28, 45.2%), community healing (24, 38.7%), and memorialisation of trauma (18, 29.0%) followed.

Figure 2. Reconstruction support and aspects respondents prioritised for reconstruction (N = 62). Panel A shows responses to the single-select item on whether the Buddhas should be reconstructed. Panel B shows multi-select responses on which aspects should be reconstructed; respondents could select more than one aspect, so totals exceed N by design. Counts and percentages are shown alongside each bar.

On the representation of destruction in future reconstructions, the modal selection was a hybrid past-present output, exemplified by holograms layered onto preserved ruins (37, 59.7%); full digital restoration was the second-ranked option (30, 48.4%); a smaller group endorsed leaving the ruined niches untouched (8, 12.9%); three respondents supported no reconstruction at all. The pattern is congruent with the Venice Charter's requirement that restoration distinguish original material from reconstructive intervention (ICOMOS, 1964) and with critical-heritage scholarship that treats absence and rupture as historically consequential conditions (Connerton, 2008; Macdonald, 2008; Rico, 2016).

Thirty-eight respondents (61.3%; 95% CI 48.8–72.4%) endorsed the inclusion of sensory elements in digital reconstructions; 17 were uncertain and 7 opposed. Asked to prioritise a single sensory modality, respondents ranked light and shadow first (27, 43.5%), followed by scent of earth (13), echo of prayer (12), and wind in the valley (6). On the content of digital reconstructions, accurate visual appearance was selected most frequently (53, 85.5%), followed by the caves and murals (31, 50.0%), Buddhist spiritual symbolism and economic impact (26 each, 41.9%), Hazara oral histories (22, 35.5%), environmental and sensory experiences (15, 24.2%), ruins and trauma of destruction (13, 21.0%), the Taliban's justification and international reactions (11, 17.7%), and soundscapes (8, 12.9%). The dominant AI-related concern was oversimplification or misrepresentation of cultural meaning (36, 58.1%), with secondary concerns about the marginalisation of local voices (19, 30.6%), fabrication of history (18, 29.0%), and the imposition of Western aesthetic defaults (13, 21.0%); 16 respondents reported no concerns. The salience of meaning-based and voice-based concerns over technical-failure concerns is consistent with critiques of digitally mediated heritage representation as a site of epistemic and representational asymmetry (Risam, 2018; Stobiecka, 2020).

On the perception of Hazara voice inclusion in current reconstruction discussions, 19 respondents (30.6%) answered yes, 12 (19.4%) answered no, and 31 (50.0%) did not know. Within the Hazara sub-sample ($n = 13$), opinion was evenly divided. The "don't know" share is the most substantive feature of this distribution: the procedural visibility of community involvement is opaque to half the sample, an opacity that bears directly on participation arguments in community-based heritage practice (Acabado & Martin, 2020; Atalay, 2012). A more detailed breakdown of the Hazara sub-sample is reported in Section S8 and Table S18 of the Methodology Supplement.

Table 3 reports sub-group contrasts on the core items. None of the comparisons between Pashtun, Hazara, and Tajik respondents, between men and women, between respondents inside Afghanistan and those in the diaspora, or between age bands, reached $\alpha = .05$; effect sizes, expressed as bias-corrected Cramér's V , were small throughout. The sample therefore provides no evidence that the demographic categories tested hold distinctively different positions on whether the Buddhas should be reconstructed, on the form reconstruction should take, on sensory inclusion, or on the question of leadership. Convergence across sub-groups is itself a finding, and it qualifies any reading of Bamiyan reconstruction as principally a site of intra-Afghan ethnic contention. The complete contrast set is reported in Section S6 and Table S16 of the Methodology Supplement.

Table 3. Sub-group contrasts on core items

Comparison	Test	Statistic	p	Cramér's V
Reconstruction support × Ethnicity (Pashtun / Hazara / Tajik)	χ^2	$\chi^2(4) = 5.42$.247	0.12
Reconstruction support × Gender	χ^2	$\chi^2(2) = 0.36$.835	0.00
Reconstruction support × Location (inside / diaspora)	χ^2	$\chi^2(2) = 2.25$.325	0.06

Comparison	Test	Statistic	p	Cramér's V
Reconstruction support × Age band	χ^2	$\chi^2 (6) = 3.20$.784	0.00
Sensory inclusion × Ethnicity	χ^2	$\chi^2 (4) = 6.51$.164	0.16
Hazara-voice perception × Ethnicity	χ^2	$\chi^2 (4) = 4.34$.361	0.05
Hazara-voice perception (Yes vs No/DK) × Location	Fisher exact	—	.092	—

Note: No contrast reached $\alpha = .05$. χ^2 = Pearson chi-square statistic; p = p-value; V = bias-corrected Cramér's V effect size. Fisher exact tests are reported where expected cell counts were too small for chi-square.

Three negative findings should be stated explicitly. The data do not support the claim that respondents differ substantively by ethnicity on the core reconstruction-ethics items; the convergence reported above is consistent across the contrasts tested. The data do not support a uniform rejection of digital reconstruction by Afghan respondents; what the data support is qualified endorsement, conditional on transparency and community inclusion. And the data do not support a preference for digital over physical modalities: the reverse holds in this sample, with physical reconstruction the modal preference (79.0%) and digital imagery a complementary rather than substitutive option (30.6%).

5. A design orientation for the AI-mediated workflow

The findings do not warrant a new heritage-reconstruction framework. They support three design principles that extend the authors' existing AI-mediated workflow. These principles are offered as orientation for practice, not as audited criteria, and remain confined to what the survey directly supports. They sit within obligations already articulated in the Venice Charter, the Nara Document, the London Charter, and the Seville Principles.

The first concerns provenance visibility. Material fidelity and historical accuracy were each prioritised by 83.9% of the sample, while concerns about AI-mediated oversimplification of meaning (58.1%) and fabrication of history (29.0%) were also substantial. Reconstructions should therefore make their evidentiary basis visible at the level of the output, indicating which source underlies which element and whether that element is documented, inferred, or speculative. This extends the Venice Charter's requirement that reconstruction remain distinguishable from original material (ICOMOS, 1964) translated into digital visualisation through the London Charter's paradata requirement (Denard, 2009) and the Seville Principles' documentation logic (López-Menchero Bendicho & Grande, 2011). Within HARF, the principle is implementable through the Dynamic Prompt Blueprint's evidential slot structure, with those anchors surfaced in the published reconstruction record (Arzomand et al., 2026).

The second concerns rupture visibility. The modal preference for representing absence was a hybrid past-present output (59.7%); 12.9% preferred the ruined niches to remain untouched, and a small minority supported no reconstruction at all. Reconstructions that present only the pre-2001 state do not align with this preference, and the implication is that reconstruction outputs should be published alongside the documented post-2001 condition rather than in place of it. This is consistent with

heritage scholarship that treats absence and rupture as historically consequential conditions rather than defects to be erased (Connerton, 2008; Harrison, 2012; Rico, 2016). Within the existing workflow, this can be implemented as a dual-view publication or delivery specification.

The third concerns governance visibility. Only 30.6% of respondents perceived Hazara voices as included in reconstruction discussions, while 50.0% did not know. Governance preferences were distributed across international organisations, Afghan experts, and local-community actors rather than concentrated in any single authority. AI-mediated reconstruction should therefore declare, in its published record, which parties were involved in evidential, interpretive, and curatorial decisions and which were not. This transparency obligation extends the London Charter's paradata requirement (Denard, 2009) and the Seville Principles' documentation conventions (López-Menchero Bendicho & Grande, 2011), and aligns the disclosure of reconstruction governance with community-based archaeology's concern for whose knowledge counts as evidence and whose absence remains unmarked (Acabado & Martin, 2020; Atalay, 2012).

Three further observations follow from the findings but are not elevated to principles. First, the sample gave substantial weight to economic and livelihood dimensions of reconstruction, with 64.5% endorsing tourism and economy as a guiding principle. Reconstruction outputs may therefore be judged partly through utility criteria that remain underdeveloped in heritage-ethics scholarship. Second, support for sensory inclusion was present but not overwhelming, and light and shadow were prioritised above acoustic and olfactory elements. Any expansion into multisensory reconstruction should follow that ordering rather than assume that sound or atmosphere are the primary sensory additions (Bao & Bowen, 2025; Bender et al., 2023; Kirshenblatt-gimblett, 2004). Third, these principles should not be read as community validation of AI-mediated reconstruction in general. A majority of respondents expressed at least one substantive concern about AI mediation, while roughly a quarter reported no concerns. The principles indicate the conditions under which AI-mediated reconstruction may become more acceptable to respondents who already hold reservations; they do not establish that such acceptance has been achieved.

6. Discussion, Limitations, and Future Work

Three findings structure the discussion. First, support for reconstruction in some form was strong and widely distributed within the sample. Second, respondents used the term reconstruction in a broader sense than visual replacement alone, attaching importance to skills, knowledge, historical context, cultural meaning, sensory elements, and the visible marking of destruction. Third, the community layer around reconstruction was perceived as unevenly included, with half the sample uncertain whether Hazara voices were represented in current discussions. Sub-group comparisons showed convergence across the demographic categories tested, which suggests that the principal patterns reported here are not confined to a single ethnic, gendered, age-based, or locational subgroup within the sample.

Across the authors' earlier work, exploratory text-to-image generation established the feasibility of historically informed AI reconstruction; HARF formalised the evidentiary discipline required for that

process within a structured expert-guided workflow; and the paired computational–expert evaluation on the Western Buddha showed that computational similarity and specialist judgement can diverge on stylistic and iconographic grounds, with community under-representation identified as an outstanding limitation (Arzomand et al., 2024, 2026; Arzomand & Kalganova, 2026). The present study addresses that limitation by identifying, in empirical terms, what the community layer would need to accommodate. The design orientation proposed in the previous section therefore extends the earlier workflow by specifying how its published outputs should register provenance, rupture, and participation.

The limits of the study arise from the case and from the access conditions under which research on it must now be conducted. The sample is a convenience sample, and it should not be read as statistically representative of Afghan opinion as a whole. Participation from within Afghanistan was also constrained by the present political and security environment. Some potential respondents, particularly those residing under the current regime, were unwilling to participate or to answer openly because of perceived personal risk. That restriction is methodologically important: it likely affected both response rates and the degree of candour available from respondents inside Afghanistan. The questionnaire was administered in English, with translation available on request, which also limited reach even with piloting and translation support. The sample size supports descriptive analysis and cautious subgroup contrasts, but not finer-grained modelling or stable interaction analysis. The measure on Hazara inclusion captures respondent perception, not an external audit of actual participation in reconstruction projects. The article also reports respondents' characterisation of the religious framing of the destruction without adjudicating the theological dispute itself. These limits define the scope of the findings, but they do not remove the value of the empirical layer the study provides.

The most important methodological implication is that the survey establishes distribution and pattern, but not the depth of explanation that follow-up interviews could provide. The next step is therefore not a broader theoretical claim, but a second method. Semi-structured interviews with Afghan heritage practitioners, Bamiyan residents, and diaspora community representatives would allow the preferences reported here to be tested against more detailed accounts of memory, legitimacy, and acceptable reconstruction practice. The methodological basis for such follow-up work is well established in community-based heritage scholarship (Acabado & Martin, 2020; Atalay, 2012; Cusack-McVeigh, 2014).

Two further directions follow. A language-stratified replication of the questionnaire, administered in Dari, Pashto, and Hazaragi with more deliberately stratified recruitment, would improve coverage and reduce dependence on English-mediated participation. A second line of work would test the design orientation against a concrete HARF reconstruction run and document what changes in the published reconstruction record when provenance visibility, rupture visibility, and governance visibility are explicitly applied. That would provide a stronger methodological test than a survey-based design paper can offer on its own. Reconstruction at Bamiyan does not occur against a neutral background. It intervenes in a field already shaped by deliberate destruction, contested memory, and uneven participation.

7. Conclusion

This article examined how Afghan respondents sampled across Afghanistan and the diaspora understand reconstruction, authenticity, absence, and participation in relation to the Buddhas of Bamiyan. The findings show that support for reconstruction is strong, but that respondents do not treat reconstruction as a question of visual replacement alone. Historical accuracy, cultural meaning, associated skills and knowledge, sensory dimensions, and the visible marking of destruction all form part of the operative meaning of acceptable reconstruction. The study also shows that uncertainty around whose voices are included in reconstruction discussions remains substantial.

The contribution of this study is bounded. It does not propose a new reconstruction framework or claim to resolve the ethics of reconstruction at Bamiyan. It identifies a missing empirical layer in the existing literature and turns the findings into design recommendations for an existing AI-mediated workflow. In doing so, it argues that provenance visibility, rupture visibility, and governance visibility should be treated as minimum conditions for publishing AI-mediated reconstruction outputs at a contested site.

Acknowledgements and Declarations

The authors thank the pilot respondents and the respondents to the full questionnaire for their time and care in engaging with difficult material, and colleagues who reviewed earlier drafts. The first author acknowledges support from the British Council's Warm Welcome Scholarships scheme. This study was approved by the Brunel University of London Research Ethics Committee under reference 50187-LR-Jan/2025-53624-2. Participation was voluntary, and no identifiable information was collected. No respondents were compensated. The anonymised dataset, full questionnaire instrument, descriptive and contrast tables, thematic coding scheme, and analytical materials are provided in the Methodology Supplement accompanying this article. The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests. No external party had editorial control over the analysis or the text of this article.

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